

Supplementary Information 2

Updated distribution range of invasive Indian bullfrog *Hoplobatrachus tigerinus* on Madagascar. Sites with recorded presence of *H. tigerinus* include Ambanja, Ambilobe, Ampijoroa, Ampitsopitsoka, Anabohazo Forest, Ankarafa, Ankarana, Ankorikakely, Antafiabe, Antanambao, Antsiranana, Antsirasira, Manondro (close to Antsiranana), near Manongarivo, Mitsinjo, Montagne des Français, Nosy Be, Sambava, Ivoloina and Tamatave

The full list of the localities where the species is known to be present in Madagascar,

- Nosy Be (Andreone et al., 2003);
- Manondro (ca. 30 km southwest of Diego-Suarez, 12°27.56'S 49°01.29'E) (D'Cruze et al., 2006);
- Ambilobe, (Glaw & Vences 2007);
- Ampijoroa, (Glaw & Vences 2007);
- Antsiranana, (Glaw & Vences 2007);
- near Manongarivo, (Glaw & Vences 2007);
- Sambava (Glaw & Vences 2007);
- Montagne des Français [between Kings Lodge" Hotel (12°18'44"S, 49°20'17"E, 20 m) and the remains of the "French Fort" (12°19'34"S, 49°20'09"E, 334 m)] (D'Cruze et al., 2007);
- Ankarana (Raselimanana, 2008);
- Antsirasira (13°56.37'S, 48°33.27'E, less than 100m a.s.l.), (Andreone et al., 2009)
- Antanambao (13°53.38'S, 48°29.05'E, 9m a.s.l.) (Andreone et al., 2009);
- Mitsinjo (16.04848, 45.79003, 44 m a.s.l.)
(Rakotoarison et al., 2015)
- Anketsakely-Anabohazo Forest (14°18.6' S, 47°54.9' E) (Penny et al., 2017)
- Ankarafa (14°22.8' S, 47°45.5' E) (Penny et al., 2017),
- Antafiabe (14°21.3' S, 47°52.1' E) (Penny et al., 2017);
- Ambanja, (Vences et al., 2003)
- Antanambao (Vences et al., 2003)
- Ivoloina, Tamatave (unpublished records)
- Ampitsopitsoka village, on iNaturalist)
- Ankorikakely village (Antsiranana) (photographic records on iNaturalist)

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